

**EFFECTS OF DUMPSITE ON GROUNDWATER AT IWOROKO-EKITI,
EKITI STATE.**

BY

MOGBOYINOLA ADEBISI AYOMIDE

MATRIC NO: 178538063

**A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL
ENGINEERING, FACULTY OF ENGINEERING, EKITI STATE
UNIVERSITY, ADO EKITI, EKITI STATE.**

**IN PARTIAL FUIFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF BACHELOR OF ENGINEERING (B.ENG.) DEGREE IN
ENGINEERING**

JANUARY, 2023

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this project work was carried out by MOGBOYINOLA ADEBISI AYOMIDE, matric number 178538063 in the Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

.....
PROF. J. O. ARIBISALA
(SUPERVISOR)

....16/01/2023.....
DATE

.....
DR. O. P. FOLORUNSO
(H.O.D.)

.....21/01/2023.....
DATE

DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God through whom I find mercy upon the land of EKSU.
And to my wonderful parents, Mr and Mrs MOGBOYINOLA for their prayers, labour and love.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I give glory to GOD the giver of life, for his goodness and mercy that endures over me throughout my years of study. I appreciate him for standing by me all through situations from the beginning to the end, may His name be exalted forever, Amen.

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I will not be able to finish this chapter without appreciating my wonderful sibling, Miss ESTHER MOGBOYINOLA for her love, affections, prayer and understanding all through my journey as a student, I pray thy good Lord will be with you too, Amen.

Finally to my course mates, SODIQ, ISAAC, LAIDE, TAIWO, SEYI AND FAITH, for making this journey worthwhile, I say am grateful, God bless you all in Jesus name, Amen.

ABSTRACT

The quality of groundwater is the resultant of all the processes and reactions that have acted on the water from the moment it was condensed in the atmosphere to the time it is discharged by a well. Groundwater pollution which is manmade is much worse than natural pollution as it eventually renders water less suitable for use than its original state. The manmade pollution or waste used in this project is solid waste. Solid waste is the unwanted or useless solid materials generated from combined residential, industrial and commercial activities in a given area. This project was carried out in order to know the effect of dumpsite on groundwater through the following tests; pH, temperature, alkalinity, turbidity, colour, odour, appearance, etc., and how to effectually collect and dispose refuse dumps not to have negative effect on groundwater meant for drinking and domestic purposes. Physical, chemical and bacteriological tests were carried out on the groundwater near and far from the selected dumpsite in Iworoko-Ekiti area. Two samples were taken from the wells near and far from the dumpsite. Results of physical and chemical tests show that the water has colour, taste and odour. The average temperature and pH values are 26.05°C and 5.81 respectively. The conductivity values are 719 μ s/cm and 711 μ s/cm. Hardness ranges are relatively soft and the Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) are 691mg/L and 687mg/L. Bacteriological tests revealed that the waters from the study area are highly contaminated, which was as a result of the transportation of the leachate generated from the dumpsite to the groundwater. However, the chemical constituents of the water samples fall within the W.H.O. permissible limits. The result on the composition of the waste shows that the dumpsite consists of 50% of plastic, 20% of food waste, 25% of paper and 5% of metallic waste. Conclusion on the project shows that the total hardness, total solid and other parameters of the water samples from the study are within W.H.O. acceptable limit and appearance, colour, taste and odour of the well water samples are all objectionable, and the well water is contaminated with E. coli, indicating that the dumpsite is infected with human and animal faeces. Considering the health hazards associated with the consumption of polluted groundwater, I recommended that regular laboratory tests should be conducted on the wells in the selected area and they should be treated against acidity with ground limestone (Calcium carbonate), and against E coli with chlorine (Cl), and the dumpsite should be properly managed.

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